

Open Science “in the lab” – Digital Disease Platforms - Global monitoring of important crop diseases

Jens G. Hansen, Aarhus University, Dept. of Agroecology Denmark

Global Rust Reference Centre - Databases and web tools responsible

EuroBlight - a potato late blight network for Europe. Coordinator, Databases and web tools responsible

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

GLOBAL RUST REFERENCE CENTER

What are the problems

New and emerging crop diseases are threatening food security and the green transition – travel/trade/climate change and multinational breeding efforts

We cannot predict – be prepared. Develop early warning systems engaging all stakeholder groups

Science: what are the drivers of evolution and spread of new races and genotypes?, new molecular techniques re host-pathogen interaction, integrate all data into risk management and forecasting models and tools, Feed into Integrated crop management.

FAIR data and tools: harmonisation and coordination, alignments, sharing and exchange of data, effective communication and dissemination.

GRRC - What we do

- ❑ Isolate characterization
 - Virulence phenotyping
 - Genotyping
 - Epidemic potential
- ❑ Training & education
- ❑ Maintenance of global rust isolate collection
- ❑ Global tracking & early warning of wheat rusts
- ❑ FAIR data management – The Wheat Rust Toolbox e-infrastructure

Open Science practices

- **early and open sharing** of research
- **research output management** including research data management
- measures to ensure **reproducibility** of research outputs
- providing **open access** to research outputs
- participation in **open peer-review**
- **involving all relevant knowledge actors** including citizens, civil society and end users in the co-creation of R&I agendas and contents (such as citizen science)

Since 2003!

- » Home
- » About GRRC
- » Research Projects
- » Submission of isolates
- » Yellow Rust Tools - maps and charts
- » Stem Rust Tools - maps and charts
- » Rust on Barberry
- » Wheat Rust Toolbox
- » Publications

You are here: wheatrust.org News and events

CAUTION: RISK OF MEDITERRANEAN BASIN 2017 CROP SEASON ON SICILY IN 2016

Results of extensive lab tests of stem rust epidemics in Sicily were carried out. The samples were collected during the epidemic of stem rust on both durum wheat and bread wheat.

2017.02.02 | JENS GRONBECH HANSEN

Figure 11: Heavily infested fields of commercial durum wheat, Sicily May 2016 (Photo credit: Dr Biagio Randazzo). Click on photo to enlarge.

contributed to the early infections in 2016. The high susceptibility to both rust diseases.

Samples of rust infected leaves and stems were analyzed for race analysis. In the single race of stem rust was reported among nomenclature - but additional virulence on a few races known to be virulent to the combination of resistance in many durum wheat varieties reported from Turkey. Race TTTTF has complete virulence on genes *Sr31*, *Sr24* and *Sr25*. Stem rust spreading rapidly, isolates from these regions in Sicily epidemic. Yellow rust samples from Sicily spectrum (see - [New races caused epidemic](#) samples were also sent to the John Innes Centre and charts are available from the [GRRC, Atlas](#)

Field surveys undertaken by Dr Biagio Randazzo resulted in an estimated area of 20,000-30,000 ha and was most severe in many cases. Highest (40-60% average severity and incidence of average severity), then Caltanissetta (20-30% incidence in Trapani and also reported from outbreak in Sicily makes this one of the largest commercial durum cultivars, notably; Simeto

Risk Assessment

The large area infected by stem rust in 2016 and persistence into the 2017 season a likely both critical determinants, but are current unknown to susceptible varieties in 2016/17. Major risk but many bread wheat varieties may also be conditions are conducive for early infection in 2017 season.

Figure 2: Relative proportions of total monthly first detection in Sicily. Source: Cambridge University optimized for *Puccinia graminis* f.sp *tritici* the

- About rusttracker.org

Country Pages

— Country Pages — ▾

Rust tools & Resources

- Pathotype Tracker – Where is Ug99?
- Survey Mapper
- Importance of Rusts
- Stem Rust Tools – Maps & Charts
- Yellow Rust Tools – Maps & Charts
- Survey Forms & Protocols
- Documents

Contact

- Contact Details

Other Sites

- BGRI (Globalrust.org)
- CIMMYT
- CIMMYT Wheat Atlas
- CIMMYT Wheat Doctor
- DWR, India
- FAO
- GRIS (Wheatpedigree.net)
- GRRC (Wheatrust.org)
- ICARDA
- WSU Stripe Rust Alert

Alerts and Announcements

- CAUTION: 2017 season
- Alert - new races caused epidemic
- ALERT: New races caused epidemic
- AND VIRULENCE

Latest Stem Rust in the Mediterranean Basin following

Results of extensive lab tests of stem rust epidemics in Sicily were carried out in April – June

NATURE | NEWS

Deadly new wheat disease threatens Europe's crops

Researchers caution that stem rust may have returned to world's largest wheat-producing region.

Shaoni Bhattacharya

02 February 2017

Rights & Permissions

The stem rust fungus damages wheat, leaving a characteristic brown stain.

An infection that struck wheat crops in Sicily last year is a new and unusually devastating fungus, researchers say — and its spores may spread to infect this year's harvests in Europe, the world's largest wheat-producing region.

"We have to be careful of shouting wolf too loudly. But this could be the largest outbreak we have had in Europe for many, many years," says Chris Gilligan, an epidemiologist at the University of Cambridge, UK, who leads a team that has modelled the probable spread of the fungus across Europe.

In alerts released on 2 February, researchers revealed the existence of TTTTF, a kind of stem rust — named for the characteristic brownish stain it as it destroys wheat leaves and stems — which was first detected in Sicily in 2016. The alarm was raised by researchers at the Global Rust Reference Center (GRRC) in Slagelse, Denmark, and the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), headquartered in Texcoco, Mexico.

(Photo credit: Dr Biagio Randazzo)

Home > Media > News Article

Spread of damaging wheat rust continues: new races found in Europe, Africa, Central Asia

Mediterranean particularly affected by new rust races

Wheat experts examine a research plot near Izmir, Turkey, affected by wheat yellow rust.

3 February 2017, Rome – Wheat rust, a family of fungal diseases that can cause crop losses of up to 100 percent in untreated susceptible wheats, is making further advances in Europe, Africa and Asia, according to two new studies produced by scientists in collaboration with FAO.

The reports, highlighted in the journal *Nature* following their publication by Aarhus University and the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center (CIMMYT), show the emergence of new races of both yellow rust and stem rust in various regions of the world in 2016.

At the same time, well-known existing rust races have spread to new countries, the studies confirm, underlining the need for early detection and action to limit major damage to wheat production, particularly in the Mediterranean basin.

Wheat is a source of food and livelihoods for over 1 billion people in developing countries. Northern and Eastern Africa, the Near East, and West, Central and South Asia – which are all vulnerable to rust diseases – alone account for some 37 percent of global wheat production.

"These new, aggressive rust races have emerged at the same time that we're working with international partners to help countries combat the existing ones, so we have to be swift and thorough in the way we approach this," said FAO Plant Pathologist Fazil Dusunceli. "It's more important than ever that specialists from international institutions and wheat producing countries work together to stop these diseases in their tracks – that involves continuous surveillance, sharing data and building emergency response plans to protect their farmers and those in neighboring countries."

Wheat rusts spread rapidly over long distances by wind. If not detected and treated on time, they can turn a healthy looking crop, only weeks away from harvest, into a tangle of yellow leaves, black stems and shriveled grains.

Fungicides can help to limit damage, but early detection and rapid action are crucial. So are integrated management strategies in the long run.

Mediterranean most affected by new rusts

On the Italian island of Sicily, a new race of the stem rust pathogen – called TTTTF – hit several thousands of hectares of durum wheat in 2016, causing the largest stem rust outbreak that Europe has seen in decades. Experience with similar races suggests that bread wheat varieties may also be susceptible to the new race.

TTTTF is the most recently identified race of stem rust. Without proper control, researchers caution, it could soon spread over long distances along the Mediterranean basin and the Adriatic coast.

Various countries across Africa, Central Asia and Europe, meanwhile, have been battling new strains of **yellow rust** never before been seen in their fields.

Italy, Morocco and four **Scandinavian countries** have seen the emergence of an entirely new, **yet-to-be-named race** of yellow rust. Notably, the new race was most prevalent in Morocco and Sicily, where yellow rust until recently was considered insignificant. Preliminary analysis suggests the new race is related to a family of strains that are aggressive and better adapted to higher temperatures than most others.

Wheat farmers in **Ethiopia** and **Uzbekistan**, at the same time, have been fighting outbreaks of yellow rust **AF2012**, another race which reared its head in both countries in 2016 and struck a major blow to Ethiopian wheat production in particular. AF2012 was previously only found in Afghanistan, before appearing in the Horn of Africa country last year, where it affected tens of thousands of hectares of wheat.

"Preliminary assessments are worrisome, but it is still unclear what the full impact of these new races will be on different wheat varieties in the affected regions," said Dusunceli. "That's what research institutions across these regions will need to further investigate in the coming months."

To offer support, FAO, in collaboration with its partners, is stepping up its efforts in training rust experts from affected countries to boost their ability to detect and manage these emerging wheat rust races.

As new races emerge, old ones continue to spread

The already established **Warrior(-)** race of yellow rust – which came onto scientists' radars in Northern Europe

Send | Print

Wheat rust experts from Europe, Africa and Asia discuss disease surveillance and management strategies during a workshop in Izmir, in April 2016.

Read the full reports

- 1 New races caused yellow rust epidemics in Europe, East Africa & Central Asia in 2016
- 2 Risk of wheat stem rust in Mediterranean basin in 2017 crop season following outbreaks on Sicily in 2016

Related links

- 1 FAO Wheat Rust disease global program
- 2 Aarhus University wheat rust program
- 3 BGRI
- 4 CIMMYT
- 5 ICARDA

Listen

- 1 Audio interview with FAO Plant Pathologist Fazil Dusunceli on the spread of wheat rust

An example of stem rust.

- > Home
- >> About GRRC
- >> Research Projects
- > Submission of isolates
- >> Yellow Rust Tools - maps and charts
- >> Stem Rust Tools - maps and charts
 - > Clades on single locations
 - > Clades frequency map
 - > Clade year distribution chart
 - > Race Frequency Map
 - > Races on Single Locations
 - > Races - Changes across years
 - > Disease Survey Mapper
 - > Surveillance data overview
 - > Relative importance of the three rusts
- >> Leaf Rust Tools - maps and charts
- >> Vulnerability Mapping Tool
- >> Rust on Barberry
- > Wheat Rust Toolbox
- > Publications

Clades frequency map

Continent
 Europe

Laboratory
 All laboratories selected

Analysis
 SSR genotypes

Year
 All
 2022
 2021
 2020
 2019
 2018
 2017
 2016
 2014
 2013

Clade
 Clade III-B
 Clade IV-A.1
 Clade IV-B
 Clade IV-E.1
 Clade IV-E.2
 Clade IV-F
 Clade VIII
 Other

Show

Data provider : GRRC, Denmark, JKI, Germany.

frontiers
 June 2022

Wheat Stem Rust Back in Europe: Diversity, Prevalence and Impact on Host Resistance

Mehran Patpour^{1*}, Mogens S. Hovmøller^{1*}, Julian Rodriguez-Algaba¹, Biagio Randazzo², Dolores Villegas³, Vladimir P. Shamanin⁴, Anna Berlin⁵, Kerstin Flath⁶, Pawel Czembor⁷, Alena Hanzalova⁸, Svetlana Slikova⁹, Ekaterina S. Skolotneva¹⁰, Yue Jin¹¹, Les Szabo¹¹, Kevin J. G. Meyer¹², Romain Valade¹³, Tine Thach¹, Jens G. Hansen¹ and Annemarie F. Justesen^{1*}

OPEN ACCESS

Edited by: Xiangming Xu, National Institute of Agricultural Botany (NIAB), United Kingdom
Reviewed by: Firdissa Eticha Bokoro, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC), Canada; Carlo Fadda, Biodiversity International (Italy), Italy

***Correspondence:** Mogens S. Hovmøller mogens.hovmoller@agro.au.dk; Annemarie F. Justesen annemariefejer.justesen@agro.au.dk

¹These authors have contributed equally to this work and share first authorship

Specialty section: This article was submitted to Plant Pathogen Interactions, a section of the journal *Frontiers in Plant Science*

Received: 23 February 2022
Accepted: 03 May 2022
Published: 02 June 2022

Citation: Patpour M, Hovmøller MS, Rodriguez-Algaba J, Randazzo B, Villegas D, Shamanin VP, Berlin A, Flath K, Czembor P, Hanzalova A, Slikova S, Skolotneva ES, Jin Y, Szabo L, Meyer KJG, Valade R, Thach T, Hansen JG and Justesen AF (2022) Wheat Stem Rust Back in Europe: Diversity, Prevalence and Impact on Host Resistance. *Front. Plant Sci.* 13:882440. doi: 10.3389/fpls.2022.882440

¹Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University, Slagelse, Denmark, ²Società Semplice Agricola Randazzo (S.A.S.), Palermo, Italy, ³Institute for Food and Agricultural Research and Technology (IRTA), Lleida, Spain, ⁴Department of Agronomy, Omsk State Agrarian University, Omsk, Russia, ⁵Department of Forest Mycology and Plant Pathology, Swedish University of Agricultural Science, Uppsala, Sweden, ⁶Julius Kühn-Institut, Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants, Institute for Plant Protection in Field Crops and Grassland, Quedlinburg, Germany, ⁷Plant Breeding & Acclimatization Institute – National Research Institute, Radzików, Poland, ⁸Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding Methods, Crop Research Institute, Prague, Czechia, ⁹National Agricultural and Food Centre, Nitra, Slovakia, ¹⁰Institute of Cytology and Genetics, Russian Academy of Sciences, Novosibirsk, Russia, ¹¹USDA-ARS Cereal Disease Laboratory, University of Minnesota, Minneapolis, MN, United States, ¹²Université Paris-Saclay, INRAE, UR BIOGER Thiverval-Grignon, France, ¹³ARVALIS Institut du Végétal, Boigneville, France

The objective of this study was to investigate the re-emergence of a previously important crop pathogen in Europe, *Puccinia graminis* f.sp. *tritici*, causing wheat stem rust. The pathogen has been insignificant in Europe for more than 60 years, but since 2016 it has caused epidemics on both durum wheat and bread wheat in local areas in southern Europe, and additional outbreaks in Central- and West Europe. The prevalence of three distinct genotypes/races in many areas, Clade III-B (TTRTF), Clade IV-B (TKTTF) and Clade IV-F (TKKTF), suggested clonal reproduction and evolution by mutation within these. None of these genetic groups and races, which likely originated from exotic incursions, were detected in Europe prior to 2016. A fourth genetic group, Clade VIII, detected in Germany (2013), was observed in several years in Central- and East Europe. Tests of representative European wheat varieties with prevalent races revealed high level of susceptibility. In contrast, high diversity with respect to virulence and Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers were detected in local populations on cereals and grasses in proximity to *Berberis* species in Spain and Sweden, indicating that the alternate host may return as functional component of the epidemiology of wheat stem rust in Europe. A geographically distant population from Omsk and Novosibirsk in western Siberia (Russia) also revealed high genetic diversity, but clearly different from current European populations. The presence of *Sr31*-virulence in multiple and highly diverse races in local populations in Spain and Siberia stress that virulence may emerge independently when large geographical areas and time spans are considered and that *Sr31*-virulence is not unique to Ug99. All isolates of the Spanish populations, collected from wheat, rye and grass species, were successfully recovered on wheat, which underline the plasticity of host

Yellow rust

H2020 – 2018-2022

DMP month 36

A European early-warning system for wheat rust

RUSTWATCH

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773311.

Grant Agreement: 773311
Call: Research and approaches for emerging diseases and pests in plants and terrestrial livestock
Type of action: Research and Innovation action

Date: 27-05-2021

DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D4.10
DELIVERABLE TITLE	Data Management Plan (DMP) updated
RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Jens Granbæk Hansen

SSR raw data

FAIR data management of e.g. Pathogen race and genotype data

Query + poppr
Population statistics

Crowdsourcing App and Dashboard

Wheat Rust Toolbox for data management, analysis and display of data (only after login)

Dissemination of races and genotypes on interactive maps and charts

Trap Nursery Data Management System

Field Nursery Data Management System

Accelerating Genetic Gains in Maize and Wheat (AGG)

Kenya, Africa. The Nepal, Department of Agroecology, optimized for screen size 1280x800. Monday, September 22, 2021.

Proposal granted, start November 2022

AU Toolbox to handle all data

Wheat rust early warning - What did we learn

Specific tools and services

- Use of the smartphone crowdsource App and the associated Dashboard for early season surveillance was a success for both farmers, extension but also for breeders. Farmers were alerted when suspected “resistant cultivars” were affected by rust in the early season. They could then adapt their control strategy.
- Results from 100 trap nurseries hosted by the official variety testing network (VCU) contributed to “hunting the new”. VCU gained by knowing what races / genotypes were in their trials.
- Results from the Field nurseries indicated that a 75% of ~250 cultivars tested were susceptible to SR races currently present in the South of Europe. Inform about level and stability of resistance in time and space.
- The Vulnerability Mapping Tool for Yellow rust and Stem rust races supported wheat rust early warning in Ethiopia right now. This tool integrates knowledge of the environment, the host and the pathogen.

What is needed for success – some general issues

- Engage and train all stakeholders along value chains and work in operational groups or regions
- The use of the tools stimulated partners to agree upon and use common standards and protocols
- Integrate the early warning system components with existing national or regional information systems
- The value lies in the integrated analysis and view of all tools and data – and knowing the big picture

Challenges for discussion:

- Behavioural changes – agreeing on the same protocols
- Need nursing and training to get new (and existing) stakeholders on board
- Privatising of extension and industry – some not willing to share data
- Crowdsourcing – question about reliability of data uploaded
- How to make tools and services relevant for a farmer, a breeder, a technical adviser, research and policy.

Thank you for your attention

